

Challenges of teaching English to multi-level students

Sarimsakova Ziyoda Baxtiyarovna

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

Department of “Foreign languages”, English teacher

sarimsakovazyoda@gmail.com

Annotation *The students in multi-level classes represent a wide range of backgrounds. These frequently include pupils who speak English at various proficiency levels. Since they cover students with varying levels of preparation—oral and primarily textbook—they can be categorized as multi-stage. There may be variations in the literacy levels of students in their mother tongue. Both a class of multiple students and a class of multiple students who are proficient in the Latin alphabet can be regarded as multi-level. A group of senior students cooperating can be referred to as a "stage. “This article discusses teaching English to multilevel courses, including obstacles, benefits, and perspectives on how to conduct multilevel classes.*

Key words *multi-level class, teaching, challenges, strategies, methods, obstacles*

Both teachers and students encounter numerous obstacles and challenges in the teaching profession. Among the challenges faced by educators is the teaching of classes with multiple levels. Being an English teacher presents challenges on a daily basis. Numerous students with varying aptitudes, motivations, interests, and backgrounds must be managed by the teacher at once. In multi-level classes, the students are just as unique as they are. They frequently consist of learners who speak English at various proficiency levels. Since they include students with a range of learning styles, including those who learn best by mouth and those who study mainly

from textbooks, they may also be referred to as multi-level classes. There may be differences in students' native language reading proficiency.

Jones claims that every class is multileveled and that different students will have varying degrees of language proficiency even if they have studied together all along. They bring their personalities, learning styles, and strengths and weaknesses to the classroom. Multileveled-ability classes, according to Ainslie, are those in which the students' abilities, motivations for learning English, needs, interests, educational backgrounds, learning styles, anxiety, and experiences vary greatly.

Multileveled classes are a universal phenomenon, according to Bremner. Students are typically placed into groups based on various factors, including age. Regardless of their accomplishments and skill levels, they are categorized at random. In the actual world, every student receives the same treatment and isn't given any preference over another.

According to Ur, P., there are nineteen factors that contribute to the ability differentiation of students. They include aptitude for language acquisition, language knowledge, cultural background, learning style, attitude toward language learning, mother tongue, intelligence, knowledge of the outside world, learning experience, vocabulary knowledge, age or maturity, gender, personality, drive, interest, independence, self-control, and educational attainment.

When faced with a multi-level classroom issue, many teachers are unsure of where to begin. They worry that the students will be demanding and that the preparation will take too long. Budgets in multi-level classrooms are frequently tight, and instructors may worry that they won't get paid for costly supplies. But teachers can only be successful if they consider the benefits of a multilevel classroom and use problem-solving techniques.

Benefits of multi-stage learning include: allowing students to learn at their own pace; teaching them how to collaborate well in a group; helping them become independent learners; helping them forge close bonds with their peers; and allowing them to actively participate in the learning process.

Multilevel class difficulties: employing only English rules when the teacher is busy and the students are working in small groups or pairs, finding the appropriate training resources and materials, setting up appropriate groups in the classroom, setting up an efficient self-access center, identifying the unique needs of each student, and ensuring the interest of all students are all important.

Depending on the size of the class, the office, and computer access, there are various approaches to determining needs. For new students, many schools administer a standardized test. Although this could assist educators in assessing students' language proficiency in a classroom with multiple levels, standardized assessments are unable to identify each student's unique needs. It is beneficial to bring students into the office to clarify their objectives when teaching small classes. It's a good idea to make a list of options for students to select from because they might not know the answer to this question. There are two options available: primary and secondary causes.

Mercer estimate that 10 to 15% of students struggle with reading. According to Snow, Burns & Graffins, reading difficulties arise in students who lack talent in the form, content, and function of language. Phonological, morphological, and syntactic skills are included in the form. Semantics, vocabulary, and word relationships are referred to as content. The ability of a student to use a language for everyday tasks is known as capacity.

Kolson asserts that there are numerous causes of reading difficulties and that the process itself is complicated. The following categories of the more common

reading difficulties are proposed by Bond, Tinkel, and Wasson: incorrect word recognition and identification, inappropriate direction habits, weak special comprehension abilities, inadequate basic comprehension abilities, poor adaptation to the reading requirements of content fields, errors in comprehension rate, and poor oral reading.

Teaching multileveled classes can be challenging. There are two aspects to the issues that teachers of multilevel classes deal with. challenges that students encounter in learning and participating in class activities, as well as challenges that the teachers encounter in directing the course. Instructors find it difficult to teach multileveled classes effectively. Higher ability students have no trouble understanding the material and completing the assigned tasks successfully in multileveled classrooms. Conversely, less capable students struggle to participate in class activities and comprehend the lessons being taught. Because of this, students with lower ability find elementary lessons and activities useful, while students with higher ability find them dull and uninteresting.

It becomes apparent that there is a sizable disparity in the students' abilities in multilevel classrooms. As a result, students with lower ability levels experience minimal issues with self-esteem. Conversely, students who are more capable experience a lack of zeal. As a result, learning is no longer enjoyable for the students. As a result, teachers find that teaching in a multileveled classroom presents many challenges. It is challenging for the teachers to guarantee equitable and equitable active learning for all of the students. While students with lower ability struggle, those with higher ability find it easy to move forward with the lessons and instructions. When teachers focus on their more gifted students, the less talented students will find their assignments challenging and lose interest in learning. Conversely, higher ability students will become disinterested in the lessons if the teachers attempt to meet the

needs of the lower ability students. Thus, the instructor must ensure that the activities or lessons are fun for the students with higher ability levels while remaining challenging for the students with lower ability levels.

According to Tomlinson, the results of an investigation into assigning students to different classes based on their ability show that pupils have not made enough progress. However, Kelly takes issue with assigning students to different classes based on their standards. He argues that by putting them in a "slow class," people who are slow learners may perceive themselves negatively as different, difficult, inferior, or in some other way. This, he says, can have negative social and emotional effects on these learners.

Since teaching reading comprehension to multileveled classes presented a number of challenges, scholars and industry experts began to develop effective teaching strategies. These tactics really help to speed up the learning process and advance the students who are struggling.

The biggest difficulty faced by language instructors when teaching multilevel classes is maintaining each student's attention regardless of their degree of experience or proficiency. Maintaining engagement and engagement among all students is a challenging task in and of itself during any course, but it becomes even more so in a language course. This is because the teacher runs the risk of losing the interest of either the advanced students, if the course is tailored to their needs, or the more beginner-level students, if the course is tailored to their needs. In either case, some students will become disengaged and begin searching for other activities to occupy their time. The smartphone is the most useful tool in this scenario.

When teaching a language, the teacher has to break through any bad habits that the students may have. In resolving these issues, it was discovered that obstacles can only be removed when students become interested in the language instruction

approach and when employing efficient new technologies. Additionally, a teacher's primary responsibility is to communicate with students in order to facilitate interaction and grant them creative freedom. Using teaching aids and media, employing gestures and mimes, learning from and consulting with teacher advisors, and other approaches are also suggested. As much as you can, involve the students in the lessons! Speak with each student individually and address them by name.

In order to support initiatives that can advance education, syllabus designers must make the most of these kinds of studies. Having visually appealing reading materials is crucial to keeping students interested, as many low-achieving students lose interest in reading classes easily. Incorporating reading materials that relate to students' interests in sports, fashion, and activities is also crucial. Selecting the right teaching techniques requires careful consideration and forward-thinking vision. Education experts ought to conduct brainstorming sessions in tandem with the students' psychological needs. We must keep in mind that the pupils are teenagers, and as such, they are vivacious and enthusiastic. These qualities can help us and help the students, especially the struggling ones, become lifelong learners.

References

1. T. Hedge. Teaching and learning in the language classroom. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press. 2000.
2. M. Swan. Practical English Usage. Oxford, 2005.
3. M.S. Ansari. Coping with the Problems of Mixed Ability Classes: A Study in the Context of Teaching English as SL/FL. International Journal of English: Literature, Language & Skills. 2013.
4. S. Bremner. Some thoughts on teaching a mixed ability class. Scottish Languages Review 2008.

5. M. Roberts. Teaching in the multilevel classroom. New York: Pearson Education 2007.
6. C. A. Tomlinson. The differentiated classroom: responding to the needs of all learners. Alexandria, Virginia: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development. 1999.